

The policy landscape is changing – how to deliver a uniquely Scottish solution?

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The last few weeks have seen several new issues coming to the fore in this post-EU agricultural policy landscape. It is sometimes hard to keep-up with developments, yet many of the developments appearing in the press don't apply here in Scotland, at least not yet.

In England, Defra are forging ahead by slashing the BPS, aiming to withdraw it by 2027 – the biggest recipients (over £150k) get a 20% reduction in 2021 rising to 70% by 2024. Defra propose to replace the BPS with the much-vaunted Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS) and its three main strands: (i) the Sustainable Farming Incentive; (ii) Local Nature Recovery (competitive agri-environment schemes) and; (iii) Landscape Recovery (which talks of 'fundamental land use change' and creating a Nature Recovery Network).

Defra's Sustainable Farming Incentive aims to introduce a complex series of tiered payments based on achievement of 'standards' (e.g. on soil, hedgerows, waterbody buffers, agricultural and horticultural land and soils, grassland, livestock). Whilst this model appears to be evolving apace, I find it difficult to see how farm incomes (and food production) can be supported by environmental payments such as these since they are restricted by the WTO to 'income foregone or additional costs incurred' (just like our current AECS schemes). Some creative accounting may bump up payment rates, but rest assured the EU, and our growing list of trade partners, will be keeping a beady eye on this to ensure the rules are being adhered to.

Here in Scotland, the Farmer Led Groups reported before the election period and the SNP in their manifesto committed to "establish the integrated implementation board to develop new proposals for sustainable farming support and drive forward the recommendations of the farmer-led groups". It will now be vital for the sector to work with Mairi Gougeon (the Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs and Island) and Mairi McAllan (the Minister for Environment, Biodiversity and Land Reform) to agree an acceptable pathway forward. This pathway will need to focus on all that the Scottish Government ask of our land – food production, climate change mitigation, biodiversity and environmental improvement and rural community and economic resilience and growth.

In the last few weeks Andrew Moxey and myself have been working with Jonnie Hall of NFUS to try and pull together the concepts and principles from the FLGs and the Suckler Beef Climate Group Programme Board to design a 'uniquely Scottish' future agricultural policy framework. Our proposed framework provides farmers and crofters with the familiarity of direct income support – but evolves the current system (which has limited environmental focus) to embed greater environmental conditionality (the new word for cross compliance).

Building on earlier discussions amongst officials and stakeholders, this framework provides a transition period up to 2025 – when the Scottish Government are obligated to

have new agricultural policy legislation in place – and then makes suggestions for future scheme design. Whilst these proposals may appear challenging at first glance the key principles are to provide farmers and crofters additional support (capital and payment rates) to allow individual businesses to make changes, firstly by developing a baseline to better understand current performance and then use this data to make plans for a carbon smart future and start on a climate smart journey. Things like animal health and welfare planning, nutrient management planning, soil, silage and slurry analytics, carbon and biodiversity plans may feel a burden to some – but for others they will already be doing most of this. These are the absolute foundations required to start the transformation journey. If people choose not to enter such a transformation scheme, they would be unable to access capital grants and they may see their greening or coupled support rates fall – and may under post-2025 policy be faced with significantly reduced support unless they make the climate and biodiversity changes independently. In the 2021-25 period it is likely that increased biodiversity conditions (e.g. on soil health, water margins, hedgerows) will be introduced to start addressing the biodiversity crisis.

The proposed framework sets out that post-2025 we maintain direct support (unlike England) as it is easier to justify on WTO terms, and is required for our upland producers that cannot compete with global agri-food powerhouses such as Australia on price. It is well recognised that extensive grazing regimes have positive contributions to make in terms of biodiversity, economies, and communities. These future direct payments would be tiered and the amount a farmer / crofter received would be dependant on how well they are delivering against new climate and biodiversity requirements (thereby not rewarding change but rather rewarding achievement). We believe there is an absolute need to maintain support for the less favoured areas – but also believe that this should be simplified and become a top-up payment on direct support. Further we think there is a need to consider (a) a simplified small holder / crofter scheme and (b) how tenants and seasonal grazers may be impacted.

We recognise the need for transformative support – that is capital and advisory support to improve productivity, deliver for the environment, diversify, or restructure businesses, etc. There is also a continued need for competitive and targeted environmental, forestry and peatland restoration support to tackle priority issues relating to climate, habitats and species.

We are not alone in fretting over the scale of the challenge ahead if we are to deliver to new objectives. I was discussing this with counterparts in Ireland recently where they too were worried that a regulatory approach could be the easy option for Governments. To reduce the chance that we will be driven to meet our targets through regulatory approaches (caps on livestock numbers, carbon credits, etc) it will be vital that: (a) the industry adapt to new climate smart production principles; (b) our scientists help find ways to reduce emission and sequester carbon; and (c) most importantly, politicians and policy makers have the courage to let (a) and (b) deliver rather than pre-emptively regulating.

We must, at least, give the industry a chance to adapt and this framework provides that opportunity. I don't see many alternative models out there that would fit Scotland. This approach can help ensure agriculture delivers on our environmental and climate challenges in a uniquely Scottish way – a way that delivers high quality, sustainable, produce that underpins our food and drink sector and helps maintain the social and economic fabric of many of our rural areas.